

ISic2997

I.Sicily inscription 2997

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

rock face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Buscemi

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 19227

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332332

1. ἐπὶ ὑπάτων Γ (αἴου) □ Κεστί-
2. ου, Μ (άρκου) Σερουιλίου Νω-
3. νιανοῦ □ ἀμφιπόλου δὲ
4. ἐν Συρακούσαις □ Α (ῥλου) □ Βαλερί-
5. ου Ἀραβικοῦ, τᾶν δὲ Παί-
6. δων □ Λ (ουκίου) □ Βηθηίου Κλάδου,
7. ἱερείας δὲ Κλωδίας Πώλ-
8. λας, μηνὸς Πανάμου
9. ζκ, παρεγένοντο πρὸς
10. τὰς Παῖδας, μετὰ Αὐλί [ας]
11. Τίτου θυγατέρ[ος], Φαβία
12. Σφονγέος μήτη[ρ] καὶ Φ[άβιλ]-
13. λα θυγάτηρ καὶ Ἄπια, [τῆ]
14. τριακάδι εὐφρανθ [έντες]
15. καὶ εὐχαριστοῦ[ν]τες Ἀ[πόλ]-
16. λωνι καὶ Παίδε[σσι].

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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Bibliography

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